

BASED DEEP LEARNING MODEL AN EFFICIENT OPTIMIZATION FOR NODULE SEGMENTATION IN LUNG

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Abstract

Automatic and accurate segmentation of lung nodules is necessary for lung cancer analysis and it is a basic process in CAD (Computer-aided diagnosis). However, several kinds of the nodule and visual similarities in the chest make it complex to design segmenting the lung nodule. Further, the major challenge to detect lung cancer is accuracy which is affected by several factors. Hence, in this work, an efficient optimization based deep learning model for lung nodule segmentation. Initially, the input CT image is pre-processed by the RBF (rapid bilateral filtering). Then, this image is subjected to a segmentation process and this process is carried out by 2D otsu thresholding. Then, to select the optimal threshold value the metaheuristic optimization IHS (Improved harmony search) is used. Finally, the segmented nodules are extracted and classified by the ResNet-152 for identifying the presence of cancer. The experimental analysis is carried out on the benchmark dataset LIDC-IDRI. The experimental results showed that the proposed model achieves better results on the basis of JSI (Jaccard similarity index), Dice and accuracy respectively. The maximum dice value achieved by 2D otsu thresholding- IHS- ResNet-152 model is 0.997 respectively.

Keywords: Accurate Segmentation, CT Image, Lung Nodule, Optimal Threshold, Deep Learning

1. Introduction

Lung cancer is the second most prevalent type of cancer in both genders. According to WHO (world health organization), 1.30 million deaths per year in the world occur due to lung cancer [1]. Lung cancer is known as a malignant tumor characterized by the unnatural growth of the cell in the lung tissue. The rapid diagnosis of lung cancer can significantly decrease the death rate and enhance patient survival chances. It is very important in improving the clinical situation of patients [2]. Thus, it is necessary to present an intelligent algorithm for the early diagnosing of lung cancer. Recent advances in computer vision and image processing technologies have significantly assisted the healthcare systems, particularly in the analysis of medical images. In this regard, image segmentation is widely used as one of the most fundamental, useful, and well-studied topics in image analysis [3].

Image segmentation significantly improves the recognisability of an image by assigning a label to each pixel. Segmentation is a substantial procedure in medical image processing and can reveal very useful information concealed in the images. One of the most important segmentation tasks in medical images is to identify redundant pixels or unwanted regions located as background [4]. Hence, segmentation is considered as most challenging steps, particularly in CT (computed tomography) to provide critical information about the shapes and volume of body organs [5-8]. The overall performance of automated cancer detection is highly

dependent on the output of the segmentation stage. In the lung segmentation stage, it is essential to distinguish the pixels associated with the lung from every other pixel in the surrounding anatomy. Radiologists generally use a CAD (computer aided design) system to provide a secondary consideration for an accurate diagnosis. This method is useful for improving the efficacy of the cure [9-10]. For many DAD system systems, a precise segmentation process of the target organ is required, which is a fundamental step and a prerequisite for effective image analysis. In the existing works, the segmentation techniques like FCM (Fuzzy C means clustering), Otsu thresholding, and region growing and multi-level thresholding were utilized [11-13]. The segmentation of lung fields is particularly challenging because the lung zone is highly inhomogeneous. In addition, pulmonary structures present same congestions in different scanners and scanning protocols which make the segmentation difficult. It becomes even more challenging, because of the presence of nodules attached closely to the lung wall. The medical image segmentation is an important and inseparable step in the diagnosis process [14-16]. To address the above stated concerns, a new segmentation model is proposed in this research study.

Motivation

Lung cancer is one of the deadly diseases and several researches are carried out to overcome this disease. Segmentation of lung nodules is the hot research area in the field of image processing. Segmentation of lung nodules is the hot research area in the field of image processing. One of the major processes in the accurate recognition of lung cancer is segmenting the lung nodules. Though several models are introduced for detecting lung cancer, an efficient model remains a challenge. Some of the challenges are: the existing threshold models have the same grey values for both trachea and bronchus regions. In some of the works, lung nodules segmentation is affected due to anonymous shapes, nodules surrounding and visual features. The similarity of lung nodules visual properties and the lung nodules variety affects the segmentation process performance. These problems in the conventional segmentation processes motivated us to do this research. The major aim of this research is to segment the lung nodules using optimization based 2D otsu model. The major objectives of the proposed work are:

- Introduces a hybrid segmentation model threshold based segmentation model for optimal threshold value selection.
- Then to improve the convergence speed and trapped by local optima IHS (Improved harmony search) is introduced.
- Finally, the elaborate simulation outcomes are performed for determining the robustness of the proposed model.

The rest of the paper is arranged as: Section 2 is the recent literature works based on the segmentation is described; the proposed lung segmentation model with mathematical calculation is explained in Section 3; Section 4 gives the brief discussion on dataset details and implemented results; the entire work is conclude in Section 5.

2. Literature survey

Q. Hu, et al, [17] performed an automatic detection of the lung cancer in computed tomography images by using Mask R-CNN for specializing the model for lung region mapping, and combined with supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods like Bayes, support vector machine, K-means and Gaussian mixture models. The developed approach by using Mask R-CNN with the K-means kernel produced the best results for lung cancer segmentation. Related to the existing approaches, the developed approach obtained higher accuracy in lung cancer segmentation.

P.M. Shakeel, et al, [18] developed a new optimized image processing and machine learning method to predict lung cancer. To recognize lung cancer, non-small cell lung cancer computed tomography scan dataset images are collected. The gathered images are examined by applying the multilevel brightness-preserving approach, which effectively examines each pixel that eliminates noise, and increases the image quality. From the noise-removed lung computed tomography image, the affected region was segmented using an improved deep neural network, and then numerous features are extracted from the segmented regions. Then, effective features are selected with the help of hybrid spiral optimization intelligent-generalized rough set approach, and the features are classified using ensemble classifier. The developed method increases the lung cancer prediction rate, and validated in terms of logarithmic loss, mean absolute error, precision, recall and F-score.

A. Halder, et al, [19] developed an adaptive morphology-based segmentation technique by designing an adaptive morphological filter for improved segmentation of the lung nodule region. The adaptive morphological filter detects candidate nodule regions employing adaptive structuring element that improves nodule detection accuracy by reducing false positives from the CT slice. The detected nodule candidate regions are then processed for feature extraction. In this study, morphological, texture and intensity-based features have been used with SVM (support vector machine classifier) for lung nodule detection. The performance of the developed framework has been evaluated by incorporating a 10-fold cross-validation technique on LIDC/IDRI dataset and a private dataset, collected from a consultant radiologist. It was observed that the developed automated CAD system has achieved better overall performance by means of sensitivity, specificity and detection accuracy.

Y. Jalali, et al, [20] developed Res BCDU-Net method to automatically and accurately segment the lung region from CT images. The developed method consists of three main steps. First, a semiautomatic method was developed to extract the ground truth for each lung. Second, a novel three image channel generation is presented to decrease the false positive rates and higher the dice coefficients, Finally, a segmentation framework was developed using a novel deep network architecture named BCDU-Net with an encoder of pre-trained ResNet-34. The developed method performed well in lung cancer detection and extensive experiments are conducted on large LIDC-IDRI dataset.

B.A. Skourt, et al, [21] developed a lung CT image segmentation using U-net architecture, which was the most used architecture in deep learning for image segmentation. The architecture

consists of a contracting path to extract high-level information and a symmetric expanding path that recovers the information needed. This network can be trained end-to-end from very few images and outperforms many methods. Simulation results show an accurate segmentation with better Dice-Coefficient index.

3. Proposed methodology

Several research works are developed in the study of applications of image processing. Even though various approaches are designed, the major challenges are clear image and segmentation. Therefore, there is a need to identify the proper process for segmentation for obtaining distinct images. Generally, CT images are not so clear because of the illumination and noise. Although several approaches were proposed for various issues, these approaches were economically expensive. Therefore, a computationally effective process is needed for lung cancer segmentation. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed lung cancer segmentation process.

Figure 1: Architecture of proposed lung cancer segmentation process

3.1 Pre-processing

The RBF filtering is used for enhancing the contrast of the input CT image. This filter is utilized for filtering radiance of high contrast image and it is computed as:

$$C_I = Pixel(I(y, z)) \quad (1)$$

Where I is the contrast image at the value of pixel intensity. This value is on the basis of pixel y and neighboring pixel point z . Let us consider that $G_d I(y, z) = (I(y) - I(z))$ is a solution for obtaining geometric distance among y and z . Finally, RBF is calculated as:

$$I_f(y, z) = \frac{1}{U_e} \sum_{a,b} I(y_i, z_i) G_r(I(y, z) - \{I(y) - I(z)\}) \quad (2)$$

$$G_d[I(y, z) - \{I(y) - I(z)\}]$$

Where U_e is a weighted standard measure, G_r and G_d are smoothing kernel range on the value of pixel intensity and coordinate of spatial kernel for edge preserving filter.

3.2 Segmentation

In this work, 2D otsu based IHS (Improved harmony search) approach is used for segmenting the cancer region. The pre-processed image is segmented and optimal threshold value is selected by the optimization. Let the pixels are divided into two categories B_0 (background) and B_1 (objects) using the threshold pair (u, v) , then a probabilities of occurrence of class are represented as:

$$P_0(u, v) = \sum_{k=0}^u \sum_{l=0}^v P_{kl} \quad (3)$$

$$P_1(u, v) = \sum_{k=u+1}^{u-1} \sum_{l=v+1}^{v-1} P_{kl} \quad (4)$$

Then the respective classes mean stages are expressed as:

$$\mu_0 = (\mu_{00}, \mu_{01})^T = \left(\frac{\sum_{k=0}^u \sum_{l=0}^v k \times P_{kl}}{P_0}, \frac{\sum_{k=0}^u \sum_{l=0}^v l \times P_{kl}}{P_0} \right)^T \quad (5)$$

$$\mu_1 = (\mu_{10}, \mu_{11})^T = \left(\frac{\sum_{k=u+1}^{i-1} \sum_{l=v+1}^{i-1} k \times P_{kl}}{P_1}, \frac{\sum_{k=u+1}^{i-1} \sum_{l=v+1}^{i-1} l \times P_{kl}}{P_1} \right)^T \quad (6)$$

The total mean class stages are expressed as:

$$\mu_T = (\mu_{T0}, \mu_{T1})^T = \left(\sum_{k=u+1}^{i-1} \sum_{l=v+1}^{i-1} k \times P_{kl}, \sum_{k=u+1}^{i-1} \sum_{l=v+1}^{i-1} l \times P_{kl} \right)^T \quad (7)$$

Then calculate the interclass dispersion matrix trace using the following expression

$$S_C = \sum_{j=0}^1 P_k (\mu_j - \mu_T)(\mu_j - \mu_T)^T \quad (8)$$

By the trace of S_C , the computation of class variance is given as:

$$u_r S_C = \frac{(\mu_k(u, v) - p_0 \mu_{T0})^2 + (\mu_l(u, v) - p_0 \mu_{T1})^2}{p_0(1 - p_0)} \quad (9)$$

Finally, compute the threshold by maximizing $u_r S_C$ and it is given as:

$$u_r S_C(u, v) = \underset{0 < u, v < i-1}{\text{maximize}} \{u_r S_C(u, v)\} \quad (10)$$

The conventional 2-D otsu has to iterate each threshold vector, therefore the computational complexity is high. Hence, harmony search (HS) is used for selecting the optimal threshold value [22]. The metaheuristics algorithm influences the musical method of finding the exact phase of harmony. This algorithm doesn't need initial value for decision parameters. Moreover, rather than using gradient search this algorithm utilizes a probabilistic random search that depends on rate of pitch adjusting and HS memory hence the derivative information are not essential. The optimization process of HS has four phases. They are initializing the optimization issue and parameters of algorithm, initializing HM (harmony memory), improving New Harmony from HM and update HM.

Step 1: Initializing the optimization issue and parameters of HS algorithm. Initially, the optimization problem is expressed as:

$$\max f(y) \text{ Is subjected to } y_j \in Y_j \quad j = 1, \dots, M$$

Where $f(y)$ is the fitness function, y is the group of every decision parameter y_j . Y_j Is the group of feasible values range for every design parameter. That is $y_{j,l} \leq Y_j \leq y_{j,u}$, where $y_{j,l}$ and $y_{j,u}$ are the lower and upper limits for every design parameters. Total of solution vectors in HM is the size of HM matrix, HMCR (harmony memory considering rate), PAR (pitch adjusting rate and terminating criterion). PAR and HMCR are used for improving the solution vector.

Step 2: Initializing HM

The HM is the location of memory in which the solution vectors are recorded. HM matrix in Equation (1) is occupied with random solution vector by uniform solution and it is expressed as:

$$HM = \begin{bmatrix} y_1^1 & y_2^1 & \dots & y_{N-1}^1 & y_N^1 \\ y_1^2 & y_2^2 & \dots & y_{N-1}^2 & y_N^2 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ y_1^{HMS} & y_2^{HMS} & \dots & y_{N-1}^{HMS} & y_N^{HMS} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Step 3: Improving New Harmony from HM

$y' = (y'_1, y'_2, \dots, y'_N)$ is a new harmony vector and is produced on the basis of 3 rules; they are consideration of memory, adjusting the pitch and random variable selection.

In consideration of memory, the value of initial decision parameter (y'_1) for a new vector is selected from any value in ($y_1^1 - y_1^{HMS}$). the values of other decision parameters (y'_2, \dots, y'_N) are selected in the similar way. The values of $HMCR$ ranges from 0 and 1. Then $(1 - HMCR)$ is a rate of randomly choosing one number from the feasible range of values.

$$y'_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} y_i \in \{y_i^1, y_i^2, \dots, y_i^{HMS}\} & \text{when probability } HMCR \\ y_i \in Y_i & \text{when probability } (1 - HMCR) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Once each element obtained using the consideration of memory is analyzed for determining whether it must be pitch adjusted. This process utilizes the PAR variable which is the pitch adjustment rate and it expressed as:

$$\text{pitch adjust for } y'_i \begin{cases} \text{Yes} & \text{when probability } PAR \\ \text{No} & \text{when probability } (1 - PAR) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

When the pitch adjusting decision for y'_i is yes, then y'_i is written as:

$$y'_i \leftarrow y'_i \pm Rand \times d_{bw} \quad (14)$$

Where d_{bw} is the arbitrary distance bandwidth, $Rand$ is the random number produced by uniform distribution among 0 and 1. In this step, consideration of HM, adjusting pitch and random selection is provided to every variable of New Harmony.

Step 4: Update HM

When $y' = (y'_1, y'_2, \dots, y'_N)$ is better than worst harmony in HM on the basis of fitness function value, the new harmony is added in HM and old worst harmony is eliminated from HM.

However, the standard HS optimization suffers from slow convergence and is trapped by local optima. Hence two parameters like mutation and crossover rate are introduced in this work. Hence it is called as IHS (Improved harmony search). Figure 2 shows the flowchart of IHS optimization.

Initialization: Let the parameters like scaling rate and crossover rate, PAR , $HMCR$, HM , and bandwidth. Then, the HM is initialized based on the Equation (11). Then, bandwidth is updated by:

$$Bw = \frac{y^u - y^l + 0.001}{10} \exp\left(-10 \frac{I}{\max I}\right) \quad (15)$$

Where I is the total improvisation, y^u and y^l are the upper and lower limits.

Then updated Y_b based on the following expression:

$$Y_b = \begin{cases} Y_n, & f(Y_n) < f(Y_b) \\ Y_b, & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Before the mutation and crossover operation, the random harmonies φ are selected. For the mutation operation, the IHS is defined as:

$$Y_m = Y^c + (Y^a - Y^b) \quad (17)$$

Where Y^c , Y^a and Y^b are the random variables. For the crossover rate, Y_m is crossed with the respective harmony for obtaining Y_n .

Figure 2: Flowchart of IHS optimization.

Finally, for selecting the best harmony, $f(Y_n^j)$ is compared with $f(Y^j)$ and update Y^j based on the following Equation.

$$Y_n^j = \begin{cases} Y_n^j & f(Y_n^j) < f(Y^j) \\ Y^j & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Hence, by the above process the lung nodules are segmented efficiently and subjected to feature extraction.

3.3 Feature extraction and classification

ResNet-152 is used for extracting and classifying the segmented nodules. It is the type of CNN and it aims to skip the convolutional blocks using shortcut connections. It has thousands of convolutional layers. The existing CNN model reduces the efficiency of the additional layers,

Res Net has more number of layer with better performance. In this work, it is used for extracting and classifying the lung cancer. Further, this model reduces the gradient vanishing problem. In addition, this network maintains better generalization and accuracy. The major advantage is that it enhances the accuracy in classification without including to the complexity of model. It has 152 layers with the 7x7 kernel size, 3x3 maxpooling layer and 4 residual modules. Figure 3 shows the architecture of ResNet-152.

Figure 3: Architecture of ResNet-152

Res Net uses residual blocks to resolve the gradient vanishing and degradation problems in CNN. The representation of residual function is as follows:

$$x = H(z, U) + z \quad (19)$$

Where z , U and x are the input weight and output of the residual block. This network is comprises of several residual blocks in which the convolutional kernel size is changed.

The identity shortcut (z) is provided straightly to input and output with same dimensions and it is given as:

$$x = H(z, U_j) + z \quad (20)$$

When there is variation in dimensions, z determines mapping and zero entries padded along with increased dimension. Hence, the projection shortcut is provided for matching the dimension using the below expression

$$x = H(z, U_j) + U_s z \quad (21)$$

There is no additional variables are included, it is included in the form of U_s .

4. Results and discussion

This section illustrates the results and discussion of the proposed lung cancer segmentation. Overall evaluation is processed on a system with 16 GB RAM and Intel Core i3 CPU with 3.0 GHz speed. The proposed IHS-ResNet152 is compared with the existing approaches like FCM, Otsu thresholding, 2D- Otsu thresholding, 2D- Otsu thresholding-IHS. Both, the existing and the proposed model are executed on Python 3.6 platform.

4.1 Dataset details

In this research study, data was collected from Lung Image Database Consortium image collection (LIDC-IDRI) [23] that consists of diagnostic and lung cancer screening thoracic computed tomography scans with marked-up annotated lesions. It is a web-accessible international resource for training, and evaluation of computer-assisted diagnostic methods for lung cancer detection and diagnosis. Initiated by the national cancer institute, further advanced by the Foundation for the National Institutes of Health (FNIH), and accompanied by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) through active participation, this public-private partnership demonstrates the success of a consortium founded on a consensus-based process.

4.2 Performance measures

All the models are analyzed on the test set after completing the training phase. Their performances are validated by the metrics like JSI (Jaccard similarity index), Dice and accuracy. The performance metrics utilized in this research are described below.

Accuracy: It is the correctness in the segmentation of lung nodules by a classifier and it is represented as:

$$A = \frac{T_p + T_n}{T_p + T_n + F_p + F_n} \quad (22)$$

JSI: This measure compares the similarity measures in segmentation of lung nodules and it is represented as:

$$JSI = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_p + F_n} \quad (23)$$

Dice: It is used to evaluate the similarity among the samples and it is represented as:

$$D = \left(\frac{2T_p}{T_p + F_p} \right) + (T_p + F_n) \quad (24)$$

Where true positive (T_p), false positive (F_p), false negative (F_n) and true negative (T_n).

4.3 Qualitative results

This section illustrates the qualitative analysis of the optimization based deep learning model using three sample images.

Figure 4: Qualitative results of (a) input images (b) Pre-processed image (c) lung nodule segmentation (d) final image

Figure 4 shows the qualitative results of (a) input images (b) Pre-processed image (c) lung nodule segmentation (d) final image. The experimentation is carried out for three sample images. Image 1 is resized with the 255x255, image 2 and 3 are resized with the 128x128 and 150x150. From the figure, it is proved that the proposed model segmented the lung nodule correctly.

4.4 Qualitative results

This section illustrates the quantitative analysis of the optimization based deep learning model using three sample images.

Table 1: Performance analysis of accuracy, JSI and Dice of segmentation approaches

Images	Methods	Accuracy	JSI	Dice
1	FCM	0.962	0.973	0.913
	Otsu thresholding	0.971	0.978	0.942
	2D- Otsu thresholding	0.978	0.981	0.933
	2D- Otsu thresholding-HS	0.991	0.991	0.946
	2D- Otsu thresholding-IHS-ResNet-152 (Proposed)	0.993	0.993	0.978
2	FCM	0.892	0.960	0.971
	Otsu thresholding	0.931	0.953	0.983
	2D- Otsu thresholding	0.943	0.961	0.987
	2D- Otsu thresholding-HS	0.964	0.974	0.989
	2D- Otsu thresholding-IHS-ResNet-152 (Proposed)	0.976	0.989	0.997
3	FCM	0.987	0.945	0.981
	Otsu thresholding	0.991	0.952	0.974
	2D- Otsu thresholding	0.994	0.981	0.991
	2D- Otsu thresholding-HS	0.995	0.992	0.969
	2D- Otsu thresholding-IHS-ResNet-152 (Proposed)	0.998	0.995	0.993

Table 1 presents the performance analysis of accuracy, JSI and Dice of segmentation approaches. The approaches like FCM, Otsu thresholding, 2D- Otsu thresholding, 2D- Otsu thresholding-IHS and Proposed methods are compared. Further, the metrics like accuracy, Dice and JSI are compared. While comparing the accuracy and JSI performance of the all models, third image obtained better values of 0.998 and 0.995 on the LIDC dataset. Moreover, when comparing the dice performance, second image obtained better value of 0.997. The existing model FCM doesn't achieve better results because it takes more time for segmentation and sensitive to noise. Then the Otsu model doesn't select the threshold value properly. 2D- Otsu thresholding-HS has a drawback of slow convergence and trapped by local optima. The proposed model obtained better results because of better optimal threshold value selection and better classification.

5. Conclusion

Automatic and accurate segmentation of lung nodule is major for the analysis of lung cancer and it is a fundamental process in CAD systems. This paper had developed hybrid optimization model 2D- Otsu thresholding-HS and classification model ResNet-152 for lung nodule segmentation and classification. Initially, the input CT image was pre-processed, segmented and classified on LIDC-IDRI dataset. Three images are considered for the experimentation process and the performances like accuracy, JSI and dice performances were compared. The qualitative and quantitative analyses were carried out. The qualitative analysis was carried by resizing the images into various sizes. The proposed model accurately segmented the lung nodule. While comparing the quantitative analysis, the three images 1, 2 and 3 achieved better

accuracy of 0.993, 0.976, and 0.998 respectively. Finally, it is proved that this model can be efficiently utilized in medical field for lung cancer diagnosis.

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